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ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF WASTE LUBRICATING OIL ON SOIL QUALITY IN AUTOMOBILE WORKSHOPS IN DELTA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the impact of waste lubricating oil (WLO) management on soil quality in automobile workshops across three local government areas in Delta State, Nigeria. Soil samples were collected using a soil auger from five sites in Uvwie, Warri, Oghara and Sapele automobile workshops. Physicochemical and heavy metal analyses were conducted to evaluate contamination levels. Results showed moderately acidic soils (pH 4.60–7.20) except WARS1, which was slightly basic. Cadmium concentrations exceeded WHO limits, while heavy metals followed the trend Cr > Zn > Pb > Cd. Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) were high (724.09–8630.39 µg/kg), indicating hydrocarbon contamination. ANOVA showed significant variation only in Total Organic Carbon (TOC%) and n-hexadecane, while PCA explained 96% of the dataset variance. The TPH contamination trend was WARS2 > SAPS2 > WARS1 > OGHS1 > SAPS1. The study concludes that improper WLO disposal significantly degrades soil quality, posing ecological and sustainability risks.

Keywords: Automobile workshops, waste lube oil, soils, total petroleum hydrocarbons

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Human beings have developed various tools to enhance living conditions and enable transportation, with fossil fuel extraction playing a key role in powering machinery and vehicles, thus improving the quality of life. However, these advancements come with significant drawbacks. The energy and chemicals used in their production can have adverse effects on both the environment and human health. The manufacturing and use of these products, combined with inadequate waste disposal practices, have resulted in the release of numerous harmful compounds into the environment, contaminating soil, groundwater, sediments, and the food chain (Busari *et al.*, 2015). Environmental pollution

has become a persistent issue in modern society, threatening vital resources such as agricultural land, drinking water, and the air we breathe (Obafemi *et al.*, 2012).

Crude oil, due to its wide-ranging applications, is one of the most environmentally damaging substances (Jolaoso, *et al.*, 2019). The chemical components of crude oil, collectively known as Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPHs) (Ogoko and Ijeoma, 2016), pose significant risks to both plants and humans when they contaminate soil and water (Ochijenu, 2023). These hydrocarbons, ranging from C8 to C40, include a complex mixture of aromatic (carbon ring) and aliphatic (straight-chain carbon) compounds, as well as volatile and semi-

volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which are major pollutants (Chokor, 2021).

Auto-mechanic workshops, also known as garages or repair shops, generate waste during the maintenance and repair of vehicles, including heavy machinery engines (EEA, 2025). These wastes contain a variety of toxic chemicals, such as aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons, polychlorinated biphenyls, chlorodibenzofurans, lubricant additives, decomposition products, and heavy metals like silicon, manganese, nickel, aluminium, and chromium (Rotimi and Ekperusi) (Wang *et al.*, 2000). When these contaminants are not properly managed, they end up polluting the soil, water, and air (Adesuyi, 2015), posing serious health risks to both humans and the environment (Abidemi, 2011). TPHs, when released into the environment, can seep from soil into underground water sources. While some soil organisms can break down certain pollutants, others may persist for extended periods, causing long-term health impacts (Chen *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, the improper disposal of used batteries, metal scraps, and motor oils by automobile mechanics further

contributes to environmental contamination (Adewuyi *et al.*, 2012). Due to their low solubility, waste oils can seep into the earth and sediments, endangering subterranean water sources and other ecosystems (Abdulkareem *et al.*, 2014 & Anoliefo *et al.*, 2001).

This study aims to assess pollution levels in soil resulting from improper waste lubricating oil disposal by automobile workshops in Delta State, Nigeria. Specifically, it evaluates physicochemical properties, TPH concentrations, explores sustainable waste oil management options, and generates a data bank on soil quality in the study areas.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted in Delta State, located in the South-South region of Nigeria. The soil samples were collected from automobile mechanic workshops within Delta State. A total of four automobile mechanic workshops were visited. The study area was divided into four sites; these sites are located in three (3) local government areas (LGAs). The systematic stratified sampling method was used to select the sample areas. These include:

Figure 1: Map showing Sampled Stations.

2.1 Sample Collection

During the sampling period, field trips were conducted within the designated sampling locations. All field equipment, including digital instruments such as pH meters, electrical conductivity meters, dissolved oxygen (DO) meters, total dissolved solids (TDS) meters, and temperature probes, was checked and calibrated according to the manufacturer's specifications before use in the field.

A hand-driven stainless-steel Soil Auger was used to collect samples from 0-15 cm (topsoil) and 15- 30 cm (subsoil) depths for organic analysis. About 100g of soil samples from each site were placed into a black polyethene bag and labelled before transporting them to the laboratory using the modified method (Olukanni and Adebisi, 2012, & Owa, 1992). Composite samples were collected from each area used for sampling.

2.2 Measurement of Physicochemical Parameters

2.2.1 pH/Electrical Conductivity: The pH (Hanna Instrument, UK) meter was first of all calibrated using buffer tablets 4,7 and 9. After this, the pH of the soil was measured using the calibrated pH meter as stated by Njoku *et al.* (2016). The conductivity meter (HACH C0150) was calibrated using 0.01M of potassium chloride (KCL). The value indicated on the meter after measurement was recorded. Finally, the meters were rinsed with deionised water between samples (Joel and Amajuoyi, 2009).

2.2.2. Soil Temperature: Soil temperature is measured using a liquid-in-glass thermometer, which uses the principle of rising liquid in a tube in close contact with the soil and media (Childs *et al.*, 2000).

2.2.3 Total Organic Carbon (TOC): The Walkey and Black method was used to estimate the soil's total organic carbon (TOC). Based on this procedure, the rapid wet oxidation method was used to determine total organic carbon.

2.2.4 Nitrate: The colorimetric method stated by the British Standard Institution (2013), was also used. This was done by using brucine and sulphuric acid to develop colour and then the absorbance was read with a UV/Visible Spectrophotometer (JENWAY 6320D). Standard nitrate solution was treated as the reference and a standard curve was plotted from which the nitrate concentration in the soil was calculated.

2.2.5 Sulphate: The turbidimetric method (using a turbidity meter HACH C0150) based on chemical analysis of Ecological Matter (second edition) and APHA 4500-SO₄²⁻ was used for the determination of sulphate in soil.

2.2.6 Phosphate: This was done by the colorimetric method using the molybdenum blue ascorbic acid colour development method as reported by Imhontu *et al* (2019). The absorbance of the mixtures was read at 880 nm using a UV/VIS spectrometer.

2.2.7 Heavy metals: Heavy metals were analysed according to the method described by Hseu *et al.* 2002. The soil sample was air-dried for 3 days and sieved. 1g of the sample was weighed into a 250 mL boiling tube and digested with 10 mL of aqua regia (acid mixture). The digest was diluted with about 20 mL of distilled water and filtered into a 100 ml standard flask. This was then made up to mark and the digest was taken to AAS for analysis of Pb, Cr, Cd and Zn.

2.2.8 Cation Exchange Capacity

10 g of the air-dried soil was weighed into a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask. 50ml of 1N ammonium acetate extracting solution was added and shaken for 30 minutes. It was filtered into sample bottles and then taken to the Flame photometer (Sherwood 420) for analysis. The Na was determined alongside the standard.

2.2.9 Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH)

Extraction Procedure

Samples were extracted using the modified (US EPA 2015) method for the GC analysis of Diesel Range Organics (DRO). 10g of the air-dried and sieved soil samples and 2g of sodium sulphate were weighed and transferred into a reaction vessel. 40 ml of analytical grade n-hexane was added. The solution was then placed in a sonic bath for 30 minutes to enhance the extraction process. The sample was then filtered using a Whatman Filter paper into a pre-cleaned amber glass vessel. The filtrate was then concentrated down using a blow-down apparatus with compressed air to about <1 mL.

Sample clean-up and analysis of TPHs from samples

The sample was then cleaned up using a silica gel column and eluted with 20 ml of hexane. The eluate was again concentrated to 1 ml using the blow-down apparatus for GC injection.

3.0 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Basic statistical measurements of descriptive statistics such as the mean, standard deviation, standard error, 95% confidence interval (lower

bound and upper bound) and minimum and maximum values were performed. Using Parametric Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), inter-station comparisons were carried out to test for significant differences in chemical conditions and PAH levels. Clustered Column charts were also carried out to show the different trends at one glance. Factor analysis via principal component analysis (PCA) extractions was done which uses a dimension reduction technique. Correlation analysis was also performed to determine the interaction between the parameters analysed.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the physicochemical characteristics of soil samples from the five sampling sites are presented in Figure 2. All the soils were moderately acidic apart from WARS1, which was slightly basic with a range of 4.60 - 7.20. Comparing it with contaminated soils in a study in Warri (Ogoko and Ijeoma, 2016), the pH was also observed to be slightly acidic, with a range from 5.42 to 6.4. Maximum soil fertility exists in the pH range of 6.0 to 7.2 (Morsin *et al.*, 2014) which was observed in WARS1 and SAPSI, while the other locations were acidic. The acidic nature of the other locations may be a result of the long existence of the automobile workshop (WARS2 and SAPS2) and the large number of waste lube oil (WLO) spills that occurred in these locations. The conductivity ranged from 124 -256 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$, which was within the NESREA soil quality guidelines (400 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$). WARS1 had the highest concentrations of Nitrate and Phosphate, while SAPSI was observed to have increased levels of sulphate concentration (51.458mg/kg) compared to other locations.

Nitrate levels were above the WHO standards for OGHS1 and WARSI. Meanwhile, all the sulphate and phosphate concentrations fell within the WHO permissible limits apart from WARSS1, which recorded higher levels of phosphate (722mg/kg). The concentration of Cd was highest at WARS2 and had the trend $WARS2 > WARS1 = SAPS2 = OGHS1$. It was also observed that the concentration of Cd in all the locations was above the WHO maximum permissible standards for soil quality, apart from SAPS1, which was observed to be below the detection limit (BDL). These high levels may be due to the presence of auto battery repairers within the automobile workshops. Hence, spent car batteries, which are the major source of Cadmium, are discharged into the environment according to (Alaekwe *et al.*, 2019). Another parameter of interest was Pb, which followed the trend $WARS2 > OGHS1 = SAPS2 = WARS1$ and $> SAPS1$ and was observed to be within the permissible limit in all four locations. The respondents in all the locations, plants, man and animals are exposed to a risk

which calls for concern because these pollutants can seep into underground water, thereby leading to detrimental health effects.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics of Physicochemical Properties of the Soil Samples

At a glance, in Figure 2, it was observed that the soil sample from Warri (i.e. WARS1) is dominated by the phosphate parameter with over 700 mg/Kg. This is also evident in Table 1 showing other computed descriptive statistics, for the same set of data in the Clustered Column (CC) - Chart (Figure 2). The heavy metal profile of the automobile workshop showed an average distribution pattern of $Cr > Zn > Pb > Cd$. Comparing our results with the heavy metals profile of the mechanical automobile workshop in Lagos mainland [18], showed a slightly different average distribution pattern of $Cu > Pb > Zn > Ni > Cd$. All the different environments showed variations in the level of metals detected, which may be attributed to the level of activities ongoing.

Figure 2: Clustered Column Chart (CC-Chart) of the physicochemical properties of the soil data from Automobile workshops

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the physicochemical properties of soil data

Parameter	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
pH	5	5.88	1.06	.48	4.56	7.20	4.60	7.20
Temperature	5	32.80	.45	.20	32.24	33.36	32.00	33.00
Conductivity	5	168.80	50.92	22.77	105.57	232.03	124.00	254.00
Nitrate	5	153.30	121.28	54.24	2.71	303.88	70.14	366.81
Sulphate	5	38.84	8.24	3.69	28.61	49.07	31.82	51.46
Phosphate	5	277.61	250.94	112.22	-33.97	589.19	140.30	722.20
TOC	5	7.33	2.27	1.02	4.51	10.15	5.25	9.96
CEC	5	77.52	11.21	5.01	63.60	91.44	60.60	87.90
Pb	5	2.20	1.10	.49	.84	3.56	1.00	4.00
Cd	5	1.00	.70	.31	.13	1.88	.01	2.00
Cr	5	29.40	3.44	1.54	25.13	33.67	26.00	34.00
Zn	5	26.40	25.86	11.57	-5.71	58.51	8.00	70.00
Total	60	68.42	112.01	14.46	39.49	97.36	.01	722.20

4.2 Analysis of Variance for the Physicochemical Properties of the Soil Samples

The results of the ANOVA were not significant for all the parameters across the sites/samples except for the parameter *TOC (%)*. That is, all

the parameters, except *TOC (%)*, possess means that are not significantly different across the five sites/samples.

4.3: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) results of the soil data.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of the Physicochemical Parameters in the soil data.

	<i>pH</i>	<i>Temp.</i>	<i>Cond.</i>	<i>Nitrate</i>	<i>Sulphate</i>	<i>Phoshate</i>	<i>TOC</i>	<i>CEC</i>	<i>Pb</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Zn</i>
<i>pH</i>	1	-0.1681	0.8808	0.6899	0.0760	0.6582	0.7619	-0.5267	0.1544	0.0679	0.2763	0.0094
<i>Temp.</i>	-0.1681	1	0.0527	0.3833	-0.8559	0.3008	0.4387	-0.5176	0.6124	0.7882	0.2278	-0.9425
<i>Cond.</i>	0.8808	0.0527	1	0.9104	-0.1316	0.8942	0.6679	-0.4206	-0.0036	0.0136	0.6751	-0.2592
<i>Nitrate</i>	0.6899	0.3833	0.9104	1	-0.2940	0.9880	0.6637	-0.3941	0.0509	0.1590	0.6795	-0.5024
<i>Sulph.</i>	0.0760	-0.8559	-0.1316	-0.2940	1	-0.1729	-0.4682	0.6849	-0.7055	-0.8158	-0.4079	0.9512
<i>Phosh.</i>	0.6582	0.3008	0.8942	0.9880	-0.1729	1	0.5586	-0.2512	-0.0956	0.0193	0.6795	-0.4050
<i>TOC</i>	0.7619	0.4387	0.6679	0.6637	-0.4682	0.5586	1	-0.9087	0.7073	0.6873	0.1511	-0.5176
<i>CEC</i>	-0.5267	-0.5176	-0.4206	-0.3941	0.6849	-0.2512	-0.9087	1	-0.9002	-0.8620	-0.0911	0.6207
<i>Pb</i>	0.1544	0.6124	-0.0036	0.0509	-0.7055	-0.0956	0.7073	-0.9002	1	0.9692	-0.2259	-0.6036
<i>Cd</i>	0.0679	0.7882	0.0136	0.1590	-0.8158	0.0193	0.6873	-0.8620	0.9692	1	-0.1049	-0.7634
<i>Cr</i>	0.2763	0.2278	0.6751	0.6795	-0.4079	0.6795	0.1511	-0.0911	-0.2259	-0.1049	1	-0.4807
<i>Zn</i>	0.0094	-0.9425	-0.2592	-0.5024	0.9512	-0.4050	-0.5176	0.6207	-0.6036	-0.7634	-0.4807	1

Table 3: Loadings of the PCA of the soil data

	1	2	3
<i>pH</i>	-0.51465	-0.6461	-0.55846
<i>Temperature (°C)</i>	-0.73209	0.44344	0.421806
<i>Conductivity (µs/cm)</i>	-0.63148	-0.7626	-0.09939
<i>Nitrate (mg/kg)</i>	-0.73834	-0.6272	0.14288
<i>Sulphate (mg/kg)</i>	0.780491	-0.4569	-0.35844
<i>Phosphate (mg/kg)</i>	-0.62809	-0.7101	0.186437
<i>TOC (%)</i>	-0.88463	-0.0946	-0.45016
<i>CEC (meq /100g)</i>	0.865677	-0.2409	0.399079
<i>Pb (mg/kg)</i>	-0.68695	0.62766	-0.36231
<i>Cd (mg/kg)</i>	-0.7628	0.62673	-0.15068
<i>Cr (mg/kg)</i>	-0.45061	-0.5405	0.598176
<i>Zn (mg/kg)</i>	0.843221	-0.2981	-0.44708

Table 3 is the results of the different steps of the PCA for the soil data in Table 3. Table 3 contains the loadings, i.e. the correlation between the original variable and the principal components, showing which variables are the more important factors contributing to the overall variability in the study.

The three PCs explain approximately 96% of the total variation in the dataset. The first principal component possesses the strongest correlations with the parameters: Temperature,

Nitrate, Sulphate, TOC, CEC, Pb, Cd and Zn and explains 52.07% of the total variation in physicochemical properties (PCP) of the soil samples across the five sites/locations; the second principal component, having strong correlations with the parameters: pH, Conductivity and Phosphate, explains 29.47% of the total variation while the third principal component, with mild correlation with Cr and pH (which has been seen to possess a stronger correlation with the first principal component)

explains 14.64% of the total variation in physicochemical properties of the soil samples across the five sites/locations. The remaining 3.82% accrued to PC4 is not reported here because there were low correlations between the component and all the PCP of the data in Table 3. Moreover, the parameters were all negatively correlated with the PCs except Sulphate, CEC & Zn for PC1 and Cr for PC3. This means that the new variables (aggregate soil properties) represented by each PC will be affected negatively by all the parameters except those which are positively correlated with the PCs and are listed immediate forgoing lines.

4.4 Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH) in Soil samples collected from Automobile workshops

Table 4 below shows the concentrations of TPH in soil samples collected from automobile workshops in Delta State. The results from the laboratory revealed a very high content of hydrocarbons in some of the locations sampled. This implies that there were high levels of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon in the soil in each location, ranging from \sum TPH 724.0888 to 8630.3933 μ g/kg across the five sample locations. However, these values were observed to be within the permissible limits (50,000 μ g/kg) of the USEPA, Guidelines, 2017. The result shows that the continuous disposal of waste lube oil in the sampled locations will, over time, expose respondents to

a high risk of carcinogenic materials, which is of concern and therefore requires urgent bioremediation measures or the use of a thermal desorption process to curb the risk.

The concentration of TPH followed the trend: Pristine > n-nondecane > n-tridecane > n-heptadecane > n-octadecane > phytane > n-nonane > n-eicosane > n-hexadecane > n-pentadecane > n-dodecane > n-octane > n-octacosane > n-heptacosane > n-heneicosane > n-undecane > n-tetracosane > n-nonacosane > n-tricosane > n-docasane > n-tricontane > n-hentriacontane > n-dotriacontane > n-tritriacontane > n-decane > n-pentacosane > n-tetradecane > hexacosane. The average concentration variation of the priority TPHs was slightly different from a similar study carried out in Lagos (Chen *et al.*, 2019) and Warri (Li *et al.*, 2010). This may be a result of the different activities going on in the automobile workshops.

4.4.1. Descriptive Statistics for Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPH) in the Soil Samples

The descriptive statistics for TPHs are represented below, starting with the clustered column chart for the TPH concentrations in the soil samples collected for automobile workshops (Figure 3). Table 4 also gives the mean, standard deviation, standard error, 95% confidence intervals and the minimum and maximum range of values for the TPHs in soil.

Figure 3: Clustered Column Chart (CC-Chart) of the TPH in soil samples data

It can be observed from Figure 3 that n-tridecane, with a prominent concentration of 1562.1356 µg/kg, was only present in WARS2, which was the highest concentration level recorded, but was not detected in the other 4 locations sampled. At one glance, higher

concentrations were observed for pristane within a range of 35.1436 - 1990.6766 µg/kg for three locations sampled compared to other TPHs, while pristane was not detected in the fourth location, which is OGHS1.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of the TPHs in the Soil Samples

Parameter	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
					n-octane	5		
n-nonane	5	125.93	92.17	41.22	11.48	240.37	.01	240.57
n-decane	5	7.75	16.40	7.33	-12.60	28.11	.01	37.07
n-undecane	5	53.57	62.28	27.85	-23.76	130.89	.01	153.87
n-dodecane	5	92.21	187.16	83.70	-140.18	324.59	.01	426.72
n-tridecane	5	312.44	698.60	312.43	-555.00	1179.87	.01	1562.14
n-tetradecane	5	2.29	3.55	1.59	-2.12	6.70	.01	8.10
n-pentadecane	5	93.78	99.13	44.33	-29.31	216.87	1.69	230.31
n-hexadecane	5	96.16	124.08	55.49	-57.91	250.23	4.57	256.03
n-heptadecane	5	162.60	211.80	94.72	-100.38	425.58	.01	456.79
Pristine	5	960.45	895.82	400.62	-151.86	2072.76	.01	1990.68
n-octadecane	5	153.72	275.72	123.31	-188.63	496.08	.01	638.09
Phytane	5	153.56	343.35	153.55	-272.76	579.88	.01	767.76
n-nonadecane	5	459.47	262.67	117.47	133.32	785.62	303.20	922.67
n-eicosane	5	113.41	213.84	95.63	-152.10	378.93	.01	494.62
n-heneicosane	5	56.82	62.12	27.78	-20.32	133.95	.01	126.87
n-docasane	5	29.75	65.29	29.20	-51.32	110.82	.01	146.54
n-tricosane	5	37.56	39.13	17.50	-11.02	86.14	2.59	104.25
n-tetracosane	5	42.73	45.40	20.31	-13.65	99.11	1.90	120.84
n-pentacosane	5	5.77	5.88	2.63	-1.53	13.07	.01	12.53
n-hexacosane	5	5.57	3.92	1.75	.70	10.43	1.40	10.02
n-heptacosane	5	56.83	33.54	15.00	15.19	98.48	13.46	99.18
n-octacosane	5	66.65	68.14	30.47	-17.95	151.25	2.06	166.36
n-nonacosane	5	38.14	41.17	18.41	-12.98	89.25	2.87	106.21
n-tricontane	5	26.04	24.84	11.11	-4.80	56.88	2.01	62.83
n-hentriacontane	5	24.23	41.20	18.43	-26.93	75.38	.01	95.30
n-dotriacontane	5	15.38	22.55	10.08	-12.62	43.37	.01	52.92
n-tritriacontane	5	11.61	9.29	4.15	.08	23.14	2.05	24.34
Total	140	117.52	293.63	24.82	68.45	166.59	.01	1990.68

4.4.2. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) results for TPHs of the soil samples.

The results of the ANOVA are not significant for all the parameters across the sites/samples except for the parameter *n-hexadecane*. That is, all the parameters, except *n-hexadecane*, possess means that are not significant across the five sites. The PCA for the soil data resulted in three principal components explaining the total variation in the PAH of soil samples across the locations where samples were collected. Only the first two principal components showed high correlations (> 0.5 or < -0.5). The values of the third principal component were less than 0.5 or -0.5 , and

hence the third component, explaining the last 10.50 % was dropped as seen in Figure 3. Very strong correlations can be observed between principal component (PC1) and all the TPH parameters except *n-heneicosane*, *n-hexacosane*, *n-heptacosane*, *octacosane*, *nonacosane*, *n-dotriacontane* and *n-tritriacontane*. *n-hexadecane*, *n-heneicosane*, *n-tritricotane* and *n-dotriacontane* correlated fairly strongly with the second principal component (PC2) while *n-hexacosane*, *n-heptacosane* and *n-octacosane* also correlated fairly strongly with the third principal component. Figure 3 represents the Scree plot showing the % variations per PC for the TPHs in the soil data.

Table 5: Loadings of the PCA for the TPH concentrations of the soil samples

	1	2	3	4
<i>n-octane</i>	-0.6595	-0.5621	-0.4973	-0.0425
<i>n-nonane</i>	-0.7483	-0.489	-0.4193	-0.1586
<i>n-decane</i>	0.97866	-0.0147	0.14445	-0.1454
<i>n-undecane</i>	0.93572	-0.2722	-0.2163	-0.0597
<i>n-dodecane</i>	0.97879	-0.0212	0.10516	-0.1745
<i>n-tetradecane</i>	-0.5222	0.14206	0.71072	-0.4495
<i>n-pentadecane</i>	0.85073	-0.3096	-0.0302	0.42368
<i>n-hexadecane</i>	0.50191	0.85857	0.07431	0.07366
<i>n-heptadecane</i>	0.84218	-0.3031	0.10293	0.43388
<i>pristane</i>	0.66974	0.4649	-0.4868	-0.3137
<i>n-octadecane</i>	0.96898	0.18583	0.12218	-0.1078
<i>n-nonadecane</i>	0.97172	-0.003	-0.0182	-0.2354
<i>n-eicosane</i>	0.97936	0.00217	0.05667	-0.194
<i>n-heneicosane</i>	-0.4859	0.5904	-0.5878	-0.2642
<i>n-docasane</i>	0.979	-0.0033	0.13459	-0.1531
<i>n-tricosane</i>	0.97643	0.11417	-0.157	-0.0943
<i>n-tetracosane</i>	-0.0482	-0.1823	-0.9606	-0.2042
<i>n-pentacosane</i>	0.56494	-0.4141	-0.6987	-0.1457
<i>n-hexacosane</i>	-0.4112	0.43103	-0.4447	0.66886
<i>n-heptacosane</i>	0.22201	0.64908	-0.1377	0.71446
<i>n-octacosane</i>	0.44343	-0.2816	0.0357	0.85016
<i>n-nonacosane</i>	0.964	-0.198	-0.1775	-0.0005
<i>n-tricontane</i>	0.88889	-0.3113	-0.3355	0.0211
<i>n-hentriacontane</i>	0.95214	0.26221	0.12103	-0.1002
<i>n-dotriacontane</i>	-0.3513	0.88796	-0.2968	-0.0021
<i>n-tritriacontane</i>	0.34955	0.90473	-0.2147	-0.1149

Figure 3: Scree plot showing the % variations per PC for the soil data

5.0 CONCLUSION

Used lubricating oil is toxic and harmful, and its improper disposal and reuse create significant environmental damage. This study assesses the environmental impact and management of vehicular used oil (waste lube oil). Laboratory analysis and statistical tools reveal high levels of heavy metals, total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH), and altered physicochemical properties in soil samples, which deplete nutrients and contaminate groundwater, making borehole water unsafe. Particularly high TPH concentrations in Delta State's automobile workshops, especially WARS2, highlight a major environmental and public health concern. Immediate remediation, such as bioremediation or thermal desorption, is crucial to prevent carcinogenic exposure and restore soil quality. This issue mirrors global challenges, particularly in African nations like Nigeria, where inadequate oil management systems lead to environmental and health risks. Proper recycling and reuse of used oil—such as using it as industrial fuel, hydraulic oil, or re-refining it—could improve sustainability and reduce harm. This study has contributed a data bank on the physicochemical properties of impacted soil, confirming that improper disposal of used oil leaves a lasting environmental footprint.

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